

Rice-based cropping systems

Effect of tillage level and seed rate on stand establishment and weed growth in mungbean

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Mungbean is widely grown before and after the monsoon rice crop in the Solana area, Tuguegarao, Cagayan Province, Philippines. Farmers usually use a low seed rate (about 15 kg/ha) and practice minimum tillage for a grain yield of less than 1 t/ha. Low plant density, weed infestation, and insects are important constraints on yields.

An experiment in a farmer's field at the Solana cropping systems research site of IRRI tested the effects of tillage level and seeding rate on stand establishment and weed infestation in the

mungbean crop. A split-plot design was used, with two tillage levels (high: 3 plowings and 3 harrowings, and low: just furrowing) in the main plots and three seeding rates (15, 25, and 40 kg/ha) in the subplots. Treatments were replicated three times.

Seeds were sown continuously in furrows 30 cm apart 10 May 1981. No fertilizer was applied. Plant population and weed infestation (dry weed weight/m²) data were collected 4 June 1981. Yield samples were not obtained because the crop was waterlogged at the late pod-forming stage by a typhoon on 25 June 1981.

Both the high tillage level and high seed rate consistently increased plant population per unit area (see figure). At 15, 25, and 40 kg seed ha plant populations for the high-tillage treatment were 55, 42, and 14% more than for the low-tillage treatment. The average plant

density/m² was 47 in high tillage and 37 in low tillage. The seed rate 40 kg/ha gave a significantly higher plant population/m² than did the lower rates. At low tillage, the seed rate 25 kg/ha gave 84% higher plant populations and the 40 kg/ha seed rate gave 269% higher plant population than the seed rate of 15 kg/ha. At high tillage, the population was 68% higher with 25 kg seed/ha and 172% higher with 40 kg seed/ha.

The effect of seed rate on dry weed weight was not statistically significant. Tillage level had a significant effect on dry weed weight. High tillage reduced weed infestation in the mungbean crop by 46%. Dry weed weight averaged 110 g/m² in the low-tillage treatment and 59 g/m² in the high-tillage. There was no significant interaction between tillage level and seed rate on plant population and dry weed weight per unit area. ■

Effect of tillage level and seed rate on plant population and weed growth in mungbean. Solana, Tuguegarao, Philippines, 1981.